

Synthesis of some 2-(4'-Methoxy- β -phenyl)ethylchromones

A. K. D. MAZUMDAR*, S. C. DAS, K. RANGACHARI, G. C. SAHA and K. D. BANERJI

Chemical Laboratory, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

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A perusal of literature reveals that the β -phenylethylchromones have not been synthesised via Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement. Doyle *et al.*¹ while attempting to synthesise such ethylchromones using Baker-Venkataraman transformation, had observed the process to be unsuitable for chromone synthesis. A reinvestigation appeared to be in order.

For this purpose, *p*-methoxy- β -phenylpropionic acid was condensed with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (**1a-e**) using POCl₃ in pyridine and the resulting esters, all hitherto unknown, rearranged to the new 1,3-diketones (**2a-e**). The β -diketones were then converted to yield the chromones (**3a-e**) by boiling

their acetic acid solution with traces of concentrated hydrochloric acid (Scheme 1). Earlier, Robinson and Shinoda² reported the synthesis of a few ethylchromones from styrylchromones.

All the chromones analysed correctly. The ir spectrum showed bands at 1 645–1 660 (C=O) and 1210–1220 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C). The pmr spectrum showed the diagnostic signal of C-3 proton of chromones at δ 6.15, CH₂CH₂ protons at δ 3.0 (at 60 and 90 MHz). However, discerning splitting centering at δ 3.0 was observable only at 250 MHz. Mass spectra of two of the chromones (**3b** and **3d**) exhibited the expected peaks and confirm the molecular weights and hence also the structure. As expected, methoxytropylium ion was formed in both the cases. The chromones when refluxed with ethanolic KOH in presence of guanidines or thiourea to produce the related pyrimidine and

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) POCl₃/pyridine, (ii) KOH/dioxan, (iii) gl. AcOH, conc. HCl, Δ , (iv) guanidine, EtOH/KOH, Δ and (v) thiourea, EtOH/KOH, Δ .

thiopyrimidine compounds in moderate yield^{3,4} (Scheme 1). The transformations thus further support to the chromone structures.

Experimental

4'-Methoxy-β-phenylpropionyloxyacetophenones (2a-e) : To a mixture of **1** (0.0065 mol) and *p*-methoxy-β-phenylpropionic acid (0.007 mol) in dry pyridine, POCl₃ (0.03 mol) was added. After stirring for 2 h, the mixture was poured over ice-cold HCl (1 : 1) and worked up to yield the products which were recrystallised from methanol : **2a** (60%), m.p. 77–78°; **b** (65%) 73–74°; **c** (62%), 86–87°; **d** (70%), 77–79°; **e** (40%), 76–77°.

β-Phenylethylchromones (3a-e) : A solution of an ester (**2**; 0.01 mol) in dry dioxan was refluxed for 1 h with powdered KOH (0.03 mol) and then decomposed with ice and H₂SO₄ solution (2*M*). The resulting crude 1,3 diketones (positive ferric test) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid and refluxed for 1 h after adding small amount of concentrated HCl. The mixture was cooled and diluted with cold water and the resulting solids were recrystallised (yields 20–40%) : **3a** m.p. 113–15° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 1645–1660 (C=O) and 1210–1220 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C), δ (60 MHz; CDCl₃) 6.10 (1H, s, H-3), 2.9 (4H, s, CH₂CH₂), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 6.8–8.2 (7H, m, ArH); *m/z* 394, 392 (M+1), 121, 85, 71, 57 and 43; **b** m.p. 102–04° (EtOH); **c** 150–52° (MeOH); **d** 98–99° (EtOH), **e** 190–92° (EtOH).

The aminopyrimidine (4) : A mixture of the chromone (**3b**; 0.01 mol), guanidine sulphate (0.01 mol) and KOH (0.02 mol) dissolved in water (2–3 ml) an ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h, cooled, diluted with water and acidified (acetic acid)

to yield **4b**, (50°) m.p. 213–14° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 3300 (NH), 1600 (C=C stretch NH bend), 1240 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 3.70 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.0 (4H, s, CH₂CH₂), 6.2 (2H, h, NH₂) and 6.9–7.9 (m, OH + 7 × ArH); *m/z* 436, 435, 434, 433, 253, 252, 251, 250, 233, 205, 203, 152, 121, 98 and 62.

The thiopyrimidines (5b and 5d) : A mixture of a chromone (**3**; 0.01 mol), thiourea (0.01 mol) and KOH (0.02 mol) in water (2–3 ml) and ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and then worked up as in the case of aminopyrimidines to yield the products : **5b** (50%), m.p. 189–200° (EtOH); ν_{\max} , 2920 (NH), 1600 (C=N), 1180 (C=S) and 1430 cm⁻¹ (N–C=S); **5d** (55%), m.p. 188° (xylene), ν_{\max} 3000 (NH), 1650 (C=N), 1190 (C=S) and 1435 cm⁻¹ (N–C=S).

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